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OMIP-117: 40-Parameter/37-Color Spectral Cytometry Panel for Robust Immunoprofiling of Human Lymphoid Subsets in Cancer Patients

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of immune cell compartments in cancer patients is crucial to predict treatment efficacy and relapse. We introduce a robust 40-parameter, 37-channel spectral cytometry panel designed to profile human lymphoid subsets and CAR-T cell expansion, with the capability to assess exhaustion status by profiling immune checkpoints and activating receptors in cancer patients. Developed for the 5-laser Cytex Aurora, the panel optimizes fluorophore selection and uses three pairs of mutually exclusive markers assigned to a single fluorescent parameter to simplify setup and ensure robust data, adopting a conservative design choice to keep similarity indices below 0.85; though higher overlaps can still yield high-quality data when best practices are applied. The panel enables detailed analysis of well-defined lymphoid subsets using a conventional gating strategy, as well as detection of unconventional subsets with variable expression patterns by unsupervised algorithm-based analysis. The effectiveness of the panel is demonstrated through a dataset simulating the progression of multiple myeloma, from pre-malignant disease to a highly aggressive stage.

1 | Background

The state of the immune system is crucial in cancer development and the progression from a premalignant condition to active disease, as uncompromised immune surveillance can suppress tumor initiation, while immune evasion is a hallmark of malignant progression [1, 2]. Furthermore, the efficacy of modern immunotherapies, including naked monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), T-cell engagers (TCEs), and chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T-cell therapies, is heavily dependent on the status of immune effector cells, particularly T cells and NK cells [3–5].

Advancements in clinically approved immunotherapies have driven interest in understanding changes in immune cell compartments in cancer patients, as specific immune cell subsets and expression patterns may help predict treatment efficacy and the risk of disease relapse [6–9].

Monitoring the immune system using flow cytometry presents certain challenges, but remains a more cost-effective and efficient alternative compared to single cell genomics. However, the size and the overall design of the panel can significantly impact both data quality and ease of implementation for new users.

[Correction added on 10 October 2025, after first online publication: The Legal Statement has been updated.]

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Fluorophore overlaps present crucial limitations in spectral cytometry compared to mass cytometry [10], and ensuring robustness together with accessibility is essential, underscoring the need for OMIP creators to address these limitations comprehensively. To our knowledge, several extensive spectral cytometry panels have been successfully presented so far to access human samples utilizing 40 or more markers, including the revised version of OMIP-069 (40 parameters for Cytex Aurora), OMIP-102 (50 parameters for BD FACSDiscover), OMIP-109 (45 parameters for Cytex Aurora), or OMIP-112 (Sony ID7000). Yet, the panel size and design aspects introduce significant challenges in terms of panel management and setup due to the presence of highly overlapping fluorophores with spectral similarity over 0.9 [11–15].

The panel presented here consists of 40 markers assigned to 37 fluorophores and was designed to combine the benefits of high-parameter analysis with maximum robustness, resulting in an easier-to-implement design for 5-laser Cytex Aurora (355, 405, 488, 561, and 640 nm). The optimization process, spanning approximately 15 months, has significantly improved the panel's performance since its initial versions. The primary purpose of the panel is to provide information on the composition of the lymphoid compartment, together with tracking the exhaustion or activation status of T and NK cells (Table 1). Additionally, we have allocated a dedicated PE channel, which can be used either for CAR T cell detection with commercially available conjugates or adapted for specific user purposes if CAR is not required. The panel is distinct for its low mixing matrix condition number (12.44), achieved by: (1) selecting fluorophores with similarity less than 0.85; (2) detecting two mutually exclusive markers in single channels—a technique inspired by the EuroFlow diagnostic tubes [16]; (3) including novel blue-laser excitable fluorophores. The panel also incorporates a CD38 multi-epitope antibody, making it suitable for patients undergoing treatment with anti-CD38 monoclonal antibodies, commonly used in multiple myeloma [17, 18] and occasionally in acute leukemia (Table 2) [19].

In detail, the panel allows for a detailed analysis of the lymphoid compartment, including subsets of T cells, NK cells, B cells (together with precursors and plasma cells) and plasmacytoid dendritic cells (PDCs). It also allows the detection of unconventional subsets expressing activating or inhibitory immune cell receptors, and enables monitoring CAR T cell expansion. To achieve a clear fraction of lymphoid cells during preliminary cleanup gating, the panel facilitates the exclusion of dead cells (Live/Dead), CD45- debris or nucleated red blood cells, and CD33+ myeloid lineage, with enhanced exclusion of basophils (CD33^{low}

CD123+ CD272-). By combining CD4+ IgM, CD8+ IgD, and TCR $\gamma\delta$ + CD19 as mutually exclusive markers across three individual channels instead of six, the panel size was reduced, while separate use of CD3 and CD56 ensured robust separation of major subsets in conventional gating and clustering algorithms. Individual lymphoid lineages can be distinguished by conventional gating on CD3, CD56, and CD19.

Within the CD3+ T cell compartment, gating on CAR+ and CAR- can distinguish between engineered CAR-expressing T cells and non-CAR T cells. TCR type can be used to differentiate classical TCR $\alpha\beta$ T cells (TCR $\gamma\delta$ -), from non-classical TCR $\gamma\delta$ T cells (TCR $\gamma\delta$ +). Additionally, the T cell compartment can be gated to identify helper (CD4+), cytotoxic (CD8+), double positive (CD4+ CD8+), double negative (CD4- CD8-), and NK-like (CD56+) T cells. CD4+ T cells are considered key coordinators of both antigen specific and non-specific immune responses, while CD8+ T cells primarily mediate the direct elimination of virus-infected or cancerous cells, though they can also be activated in a bystander manner to release cytokines [20]. CD56+ NK-like T cells and TCR $\gamma\delta$ + T cells are classified as innate-like immune cells; however, they have proven antitumor potential, as they can target cancer cells without prior antigen exposure and function independently of MHC molecules [21, 22]. Furthermore, CD27, CD28, CD45RA, and CD197 were included to characterize differentiation status and effector phenotype in T cells, which can be individually determined in the subsets mentioned above: naïve (CD45RA+ CD197+), central memory (CD45RA- CD197+), early effector (CD45RA- CD197- CD28+ CD27+), early-like effector (CD45RA- CD197- CD28+ CD27-), intermediate effector (CD45RA- CD197- CD28- CD27+), terminal effector (CD45RA- CD197- CD28- CD27-) and CD45RA+ terminal effector (CD45RA+ CD197- CD28- CD27-) [23–25]. Regulatory T cells (Tregs) (CD4+ CD25+ CD127-), which were connected to suppression of anti-cancer response, can be further detected [26, 27]. Additionally, other markers in the panel, such as CD39 and CD57, enable the identification of specific disease-related subsets, including highly suppressive CD39+ T cells and terminally differentiated, highly cytotoxic CD57+ T cells [28, 29].

The NK cell lineage is primarily defined by a CD3- CD19- CD56+ phenotype, with a well-established division into CD56^{high} CD16- cytokine-producing NK cells and CD56+/^{dim} CD16+ cytotoxic NK cells. The cytotoxic subset can be further subdivided into CD16+ CD57- and terminally differentiated CD16+ CD57+ subsets through conventional gating [30]. Additionally, other subsets can be detected by conventional gating, such as CD8+ NK cells, which have been described in the context of chronic infectious and autoimmune diseases [31]. It is also important to note that IgM and IgG staining on NK cells can occur due to Fc receptor binding of soluble immunoglobulins, despite their lack of endogenous Ig expression. However, since NK cells do not express CD4, this does not affect the integrity of our panel [32].

For the B cell lineage, the panel is designed to provide a detailed analysis, including individual precursor stages: pre-B1 (CD10^{high} CD19+ CD34+), pre-B2 (CD10+ CD19+ CD34-), and immature B cells (CD10^{low} CD19+ CD34-). Although theoretically, Pro-B cells (CD10+ CD19- CD34+) can also be

TABLE 1 | OMIP summary.

Purpose	Robust 40-parameter phenotyping of lymphoid cells and CAR-T cells
Species	Human
Cell type	Lymphoid cells and precursors (fresh or cryopreserved)
Cross references	OMIP 029, 069, 102, 109, 112, and others cited

TABLE 2 | List of reagents.

	Specificity	Fluorophore	Clone	Purpose
1	CD3	BUV395	SK7	T cell differentiation
2	Dead cells	Live dead blue	N/A	Exclusion of dead cells
3	CD4	BUV496	SK3	T cell differentiation
4	IgM	BUV496	UCH-B1	B cell differentiation
5	CD69	BUV563	FN50	NK and T cell inhibition
6	CD158b (KIR2DL)	BUV615	CH-L	NK and T cell inhibition
7	CD272 (BTLA)	BUV661	J168-540	PDC and B cell differentiation
8	CD159c (NKG2C)	BUV737	134591	NK and T cell activation
9	CD8	BUV805	SK1	T and NK cell differentiation
10	IgD	BUV805	IA6-2	B cell differentiation
11	TCR $\gamma\delta$	BV421	11F2	T cell differentiation
12	CD19	BV421	HIB19	B cell differentiation, myeloma cell phenotype
13	CD159a (NKG2A)	Pacific blue	S19004C	NK cell inhibition
14	CD138	BV480	MI15	B cell differentiation (plasma cells)
15	CD57	BV510	QA17A04	T and NK cell differentiation
16	CD45	BV570	HI30	Pan leukocyte marker
17	TIGIT	BV605	A15153G	T and NK cell inhibition
18	CD366 (TIM-3)	BV650	F38-2E2	T and NK cell inhibition
19	CD25	BV711	BC96	T cell differentiation
20	CD123	BV750	9F5	PDC differentiation, residual basophil exclusion
21	CD28	BV785	CD28.2	T cell differentiation
22	CD38ME	FITC	Multi epitope	Activation and B cell differentiation (plasma cells)
23	CD45RA	RB545	HI100	T cell differentiation
24	PD-1	RB613	EH12.1	T cell inhibition
25	CD16	PerCP-Cy5.5	3G8	NK and T cell differentiation
26	CD223 (LAG-3)	RB705	T47-530	T and NK cell inhibition
27	IgG	RB744	G18-145	B cell differentiation
28	CD226 (DNAM-1)	RB780	DX11	T and NK cell activation
29	BCMA CAR	PE	N/A	Anti-BCMA CAR T cell detection
30	CD19 CAR	PE	N/A	Anti-CD19 CAR T cell detection
31	CD335 (NKp46)	PE-dazzle 594	9E2	NK cell differentiation and activation
32	CD127	PE-Cy5	A019D5	T cell differentiation
33	CD33	Pe-Fire 700	WM53	Myeloid lineage exclusion
34	CD56	cFluor BYG750	TULY56	NK and T cell differentiation, myeloma cell phenotype
35	CD34	PE-Cy7	561	Progenitor cell differentiation
36	CD39	PE-Fire 810	A1	T cell activation
37	CD244 (2B4)	APC	C1.7	NK and T cell activation
38	CD314 (NKG2D)	Alexa fluor 660	1D11	NK cell differentiation and activation
39	CD10	R718	HI10a	B cell differentiation (precursors)
40	CD27	APC-Cy7	M-T271	T cell differentiation
41	CD197 (CCR7)	APC-Fire 810	G043H7	T cell differentiation

FIGURE 1 | Overview of the panel. (A) Conventionally defined subsets were gated within the lymphoid cell and precursor fraction, which was purified using the pre-gating strategy detailed in the Section 5.3. Individual subsets were subsequently projected onto a UMAP, providing an overview of individual populations in the dimensionally reduced space. Gating strategy dotplots were generated using four individual files merged into a single file containing 3.57×10^5 events using the concatenate function. (B) The signals of individual markers representing activating and inhibitory immune cell molecules were visualized on a UMAP of the merged dataset as continuous color scatter plots. A uniform color scale was applied across all channels to ensure consistent representation of signal intensity for each marker across the entire panel. Data were analyzed and generated using the OMIQ platform (www.omiq.ai) and FlowJo 10.9 (BD Biosciences). [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

detected, they are rare, and additional markers such as cyTdT and CD22 are needed for precise identification [33, 34]. The mature B cell compartment can be further subdivided based on the expression of IgD, IgM, IgG, CD27, CD38, and CD138. Naïve (IgD+ CD27−), non-switched memory (also called marginal zone-like; IgD+ CD27+), switched memory (IgD− CD27+), and double-negative (IgD− CD27−) B cells can be identified [35–37]. Including IgM and IgG allows for the identification of additional subsets, such as IgG+ IgM− IgD− CD27+ switched memory B cells, as well as IgM+ IgD+ CD27+ non-switched memory B cells [38]. The panel also enables detailed detection of plasma cells, with the capability to distinguish between normal (CD19+ CD38+ CD45+ CD56− CD138+) and aberrant phenotypes (CD19−/+ CD38−/dim/+ CD45−/+ CD56−/+ CD138+), which are found in patients diagnosed with monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (MGUS), multiple myeloma (MM), MM with extramedullary progression, or light chain amyloidosis [39–44]. Additionally, plasmacytoid dendritic cells (PDCs) can be detected accurately as CD123+ CD272+. These cells are often present in large numbers in various tumors and are believed to play a role in the anticancer response [45, 46].

Most important, several molecules responsible for the inhibition or activation of immune cell effector function, present in both T and NK cells, were incorporated into the panel to identify specific exhausted or highly cytotoxic subsets that could possibly be associated with immunotherapy responses or malignant progression. Inhibitory receptors included: CD39, CD69, CD158b (KIR2DL), CD159a (NKG2A), TIGIT, CD366 (TIM-3), CD279 (PD-1), and CD223 (LAG-3). Activating receptors included: CD158c (NKG2C), CD244 (2B4), CD226 (DNAM-1), CD335 (NKP46), and CD314 (NKG2D) [30, 47–51].

Although conventional (manual) gating analysis (Figure 1) is possible with the presented panel, this approach is limited when it comes to detecting unconventional subsets—particularly diverse NK and T cell populations expressing variable combinations of panel-included markers. Complex phenotypes, such as CD3+ TCRγδ+ CD27+ CD127+ DNAM-1+ 2B4+ NKG2D+, were identified through clustering analysis (combination of UMAP and flowSOM) and would be challenging to resolve manually (Supporting Information).

To fully leverage the potential of the panel, it is necessary to employ dimensionality reduction and clustering algorithms such as UMAP or flowSOM [52–55], as exemplified by the analysis pipeline in the Supporting Information. To demonstrate the full potential and functionality of this panel comprehensively, we have provided a unique dataset that simulates a real-life research analysis of the lymphoid cell compartment mimicking the disease course of a patient with gradually progressing hematologic malignancy, covering all markers. This analysis includes data from four unrelated patient samples at different stages of multiple myeloma progression: (1) bone marrow of a patient diagnosed with monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance, representing pre-malignant disease stage; (2) bone marrow of a newly diagnosed multiple myeloma patient; (3) peripheral blood from a relapsed/refractory myeloma patient undergoing therapy with anti-BCMA CAR T cells on day 14 post-infusion; and (4) bone marrow of a highly aggressive extramedullary multiple myeloma, representing a terminal stage of the disease.

2 | Similarity to Published OMIPs

OMIPs 013, 021, 060, 067, 069, 082, 101, 102, 109, 112 are similar in characterization of T cells; OMIPs 051, 069 in characterization of B cells. 029, 039, 069, 070, 102, 109, 112 are similar in characterization of NK cells. OMIP 029, 084, 102 are somewhat similar in detecting activating or inhibitory receptors. Other OMIPs were used to inspect the fluorophore-marker assignments and antibody clone selection [11, 12, 14, 15, 37, 56–92].

Author Contributions

Ondrej Venglar: panel design and conceptualization, panel and SOP optimization, sample preparation, data analysis, manuscript writing, figure preparation. **Eva Radova:** sample preparation, optimization. **Lucie Broskevicova:** sample and material collection. **Tomas Jelinek:** conceptualization. **Tomas Jelinek, Roman Hajek, Eva Radova, Lucie Broskevicova:** revisions.

Ethics Statement

The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee. The procedures were in accordance with ethical standards and the Helsinki Declaration.

Consent

All patients signed informed consent.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Data S1:** Supporting Information. **Data S2:** Author Checklist: MIFlowCyt-Compliant Items.